

Bit Blasting Probabilistic Programs

ARTIFACT OVERVIEW

POORVA GARG, STEVEN HOLTZEN, GUY VAN DEN BROECK, TODD MILLSTEIN

Thank you for taking the time to evaluate this artifact. In this document you will find detailed instructions on how to build the artifact and how to reproduce the experiments from the original paper.

1 Getting Started

1.1 Building the Docker Image

The docker image has been tested only on Linux. Please follow the following instructions to download and run the image.

```
1 $ docker pull poorvagarg/bitblasting-pldi2024
2 $ docker run -it -v ${PWD}/results:/Dice.jl/results poorvagarg/bitblasting-
   pldi2024
```

This will put you in an interactive virtual machine terminal with all the required dependencies installed and the artifact repository on the path `/Dice.jl/`.

Alternatively, one can find the file `bitblasting-pldi2024.zip` on Zenodo and run the following commands to run the docker image.

```
1 $ unzip bitblasting-pldi2024.zip
2 $ docker load < bitblasting-pldi2024.tar
3 $ docker run -it -v ${PWD}/results:/Dice.jl/results poorvagarg/bitblasting-
   pldi2024
```

1.2 Building from Source

We provide a source zip file `bitblasting-artifact.zip` in the upload that contains a `README.md` file. It contains the instructions to install the artifact and basics of HyBit syntax.

2 Step-by-Step Instructions

We run our tool on the suite of benchmarks using bash scripts which are provided in suitable folders at `/Dice.jl/scripts`. But first we describe how to run a simple example file.

2.1 Using HyBit

The following is a simple HyBit program that bitblasts normal distribution and computes the probability of it being less than 0.

```
1 using Dice, Distributions
2 DFiP = DistFix{6, 2}
3 code = @dice begin
4     a = bitblast(DFiP, Normal(0, 1), 4, -8.0, 8.0)
5     b = a < DFiP(0.0)
6     b
7 end
8 pr(code)
```

This file is already in the source repository in `examples/example2.jl` and it can be run from the Docker as follows. It would print the probability distribution of `b` as a dictionary. The probability of `b` being true is 0.5.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ julia --project examples/example2.jl
3 pr(code) = DataStructures.DefaultOrderedDict{Any, Any, Float64}(false => 0.5,
    true => 0.5)
```

2.2 Reproducing the HyBit Experiments

For each of our baselines evaluated on each probabilistic program (benchmark), the timeout has been set to 20 minutes. This means reproducing all the experiments in the paper would take close to 8 days. We provide instructions to reproduce each data point, scripts to generate results for the suite of benchmarks, reported results in log files and plotting scripts. The plotting scripts would generate the results in the directory `/Dice.jl/results` inside the docker. These results can be accessed after you exit the VM at `${PWD}/results`

2.2.1 Reproducing Table 2

HyBit: The following command would run the tool on the complete suite of 19 benchmarks and would take around 20 minutes.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table2/hybit_short.sh
3 Running pi
4 (b, p[1.0], t.time) = (2, 0.375, 53.047372905)
5 Running weekend
6 (bits, pieces, p[1.0], t.time) = (2, 2, 0.37996276587660976, 33.353380102)
7 Running spacex
8 (bits, pieces, p, t.time) = (2, 2, 19.817199154252023, 28.94471344)
9 Running GPA
10 ...
```

To get the actual results reported in the paper, one can run `hybit.sh` which can take upto 7 hours.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table2/hybit.sh
```

AQUA: The following command would run the AQUA tool on the benchmarks it can support and would take around 2 hours.

```
1 $ cd AQUA
2 $ ../Dice.jl/scripts/table2/aqua.sh
3 Running GPA
4 ../Dice.jl/baselines/aqua/GPA/GPA.template
5 Mar 07, 2024 5:57:59 PM org.nd4j.linalg.factory.Nd4jBackend load
6 INFO: Loaded [CpuBackend] backend
7 ...
```

WebPPL: The following command would run the WebPPL tool on 19 benchmarks and report their results in the appropriate file. To run rejection sampling, MCMC sampling (with Metropolis Hastings kernel) or SMC sampling, run the following scripts. Please ignore the warning that comes up. The following scripts should take about 4 hours to run.

For rejection sampling

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table2/webppl_rejection.sh
3 Running pi
4 Warning: Unused option particles given to Rejection.
5 Running weekend
6 Warning: Unused option particles given to Rejection.
7 ...
```

For MCMC sampling

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table2/webppl_mcmc.sh
3 Running pi
4 Warning: Unused option particles given to MCMC.
5 ...
```

For SMC sampling

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table2/webppl_smc.sh
3 Running pi
4 Warning: Unused option samples given to SMC.
5 Running addFun_sum
6 Warning: Unused option samples given to SMC.
7 ...
```

Stan: To run Stan on all 19 benchmarks, use the following scripts. again, we have a short version that takes about 20 minutes, and a full version that takes around 7 hours.

Benchmarks	HyBit	Bits	Pieces	AQUA	WebPPL rejection	WebPPL MH	WebPPL SMC	Stan
pt	0.0001051644490787651	14.0	-	X	8.304335872232438e-05	9.667625029881795e-05	0.0013811336627688557	4.836339744829221e-05
weekend	2.0837299496978545e-08	24.0	4096.0	X	0.01572216051811613	0.015716332357887976	0.016619963156401216	X
spacex	0.0006936783206441532	19.0	32.0	X	0.0009063510661372712	0.003240200257414601	0.018846385682092726	0.00011523008701175286
GPA	2.228446049250313e-16	25.0	4096.0	0.3615107913668967	0.01700649423642903	0.00939398516698006	0.01509807787769797	X
tug_of_war	4.508214086814561e-07	22.0	16.0	X	0.0007661819458007812	0.0006935060024261475	0.0023484663529829545	4.5069999999980404e-05
alferm2	3.482958034345396e-06	17.0	256.0	3.411889291371484e-07	timeout	0.4606322452902507	0.4387413726230113	0.001684008299999984
conjugate_gaussians2	4.920559999455065e-06	23.0	16.0	0.9999999999988386	0.0002196154018287618	0.000353649827905827	0.003184620052679297	0.00010646999999996964
normal_mixture_theta	5.491552566450064e-05	9.0	64.0	4.130437008531551e-07	timeout	0.00039068604005016436	0.0053060849940087018	0.4285801342857143
normal_mixture_mu1	0.005202264715835625	9.0	16.0	timeout	timeout	0.001360104620724023	0.02002021631502373	18.69363047557161
normal_mixture_mu2	0.003924351954347927	9.0	32.0	timeout	timeout	0.0007108377231679341	0.011493329844978816	17.69369559170412
zeroone_w1	9.404780036458005e-05	16.0	-	0.0565823032448	timeout	timeout	timeout	0.17281851324480002
zeroone_w2	0.0004511457131233347	19.0	-	timeout	1.6447032269097853	1.0432872798872307	1.662929882424623	0.23793210483000005
coinbits	2.0199331707271284e-07	22.0	4096.0	0.00253213820572778	1.6921532615760526e-05	7.731302700521539e-05	0.0012245125157163796	1.17566666666695725e-05
addFun_sum	3.81469895571751e-06	23.0	16.0	X	0.00044107795645985756	0.0016919610628578054	0.005410521008966045	8.4537301e-05
clickGraph	0.0017536999456937795	10.0	-	X	0.0007298084519565918	0.0012156426716100621	0.003400802298095454	2.8044417243022757e-05
trueskill	0.003056943235678733	10.0	16.0	X	0.00018062194188435873	0.0004216134548187256	0.0016840154474431818	6.883000000001971e-05
clinicalTrial1	5.27359366969494e-16	8.0	-	X	0.1512644812582067	0.15304611990216505	0.14944901563658874	0.0009272506487534304
clinicalTrial2	6.811962650621339e-07	12.0	-	X	0.14288003508217628	0.14300042153695597	0.14258562741641911	4.5354285714283016e-05
addFun_max	2.922977220265466e-07	23.0	128.0	X	0.00043796091957692035	0.000611316463991938	0.003264317477186009	0.00011933354775628402

Figure 1: Table 2 printed

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table2/stan_short.sh
3 ...
```

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table2/stan.sh
3 ...
```

The above scripts would immediately start sampling and record the results.

Fetching Results: To fetch results, we provide a Python script that prints pretty table and can be run as follows:

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ python3 scripts/table2/table2.py
```

This would print results as shown in Figure 1. Please note that WebPPL and Stan are stochastic tools and their results vary from run to run. In the paper, we report mean of 5 runs. For artifact evaluation, we provide script to run it once and expect the results to be within the same orders of magnitude as we report in the paper.

For HyBit, results have changed with respect to the submitted paper. Figure 1 shows updated numbers which can be reproduced using the artifact.

To run the Python scripts with the results reported in the paper (already there in docker VM), use the command line argument `old` as shown below. The command line argument ‘old’ can be similarly used for other plotting and printing scripts in subsequent sections.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ python3 scripts/table2/table2.py old
```

2.2.2 Table 3

Psi: To run Psi on all 19 benchmarks, use the following commands which should take around 2 hours. These results are different from the ones reported in the paper to incorporate the feedback given by the reviewers. We plan to make these changes in the final version.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/table3/run.sh
3 Running baselines/psi/addFun_max.psi
4 Running baselines/psi/addFun_sum.psi
5 Running baselines/psi/altermu2.psi
6 ...
```

You can print the table using the following command:

```
1 $python3 scripts/table3/generate_table3.py
2 -----
3 baselines/psi/addFun_max.psi      YES
4 baselines/psi/addFun_sum.psi      YES
5 baselines/psi/altermu2.psi        YES
6 baselines/psi/clickGraph.psi      YES
7 baselines/psi/clinicalTrial1.psi  X
8 baselines/psi/clinicalTrial2.psi  YES
9 baselines/psi/coinBias.psi        YES
10 baselines/psi/conjugate_gaussians.psi YES
11 baselines/psi/GPA.psi             YES
12 baselines/psi/normal_mixture_mu1.psi X
13 baselines/psi/normal_mixture_mu2.psi X
14 baselines/psi/normal_mixture_theta.psi X
15 baselines/psi/pi.psi              YES
16 baselines/psi/spacex.psi          YES
17 baselines/psi/trueskill.psi       YES
18 baselines/psi/tug_of_war.psi      YES
19 baselines/psi/weekend.psi         YES
20 baselines/psi/zeroone_w1.psi      X
21 baselines/psi/zeroone_w2.psi      X
22 baselines/psi/addFun_max.psi      YES
23 baselines/psi/addFun_sum.psi      YES
24 baselines/psi/altermu2.psi        YES
25 baselines/psi/clickGraph.psi      YES
26 -----
```

2.2.3 Reproducing Figure 2

Figure 2 experiments can be reproduced by running every baseline for different values of T (number of discrete variables).

HyBit: The above commands would output the result and also log them for access by a later Python script. It would take around 2.5 hours to run to completion.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure2/hybit.sh
```

```
3 (n_vars, bits, pieces) = (5, 16, 4096)
4 (bits, pieces, p, t.time) = (16, 4096, 0.5000475198272607, 138.871702202)
5 Completed 5
6 ...
```

Psi The following command should take about 2.5 hours to run to completion. These experiments need to be updated in the camera-ready version.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure2/psi.sh
3 Completed 5
4 Completed 10
5 ...
```

WebPPL Each of the following commands should take about 2.5 hours to run to completion. Please ignore the warning statement it outputs. For MCMC sampling

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure2/webppl_mh.sh
3 Warning: Unused option particles given to MCMC.
4 ...
```

For SMC sampling

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure2/webppl_smc.sh
3 Warning: Unused option samples given to SMC.
4 ...
```

Stan The following command should take about 2.5 to run to completion. As you run this script, Stan would start sampling and producing results in the desired files.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure2/stan.sh
3 method = sample (Default)
4   sample
5     num_samples = 1000000000
6     num_warmup = 1000 (Default)
7 ...
```

Once the above scripts are run, they log results at the needed location. Then one can run the following Python script to generate the plot in Figure 2. The generated plot `or_error.png` can be found at the location `/Dice.jl/results` inside the docker and at the location `${PWD}/results/` during and after running the docker image.

```
1 $ python3 scripts/figure2/generate_plot.py
```

2.2.4 Reproducing Figure 4

To generate the data and run different baselines, run the following command:

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure4/run.sh
3 $ python3 scripts/figure4/generate_plot.py
```

The above commands would generate figures `multimodal_mcmc_mh.pdf`, `multimodal_smc.pdf`, `multimodal_hmc.pdf` and `multimodal_aqua.pdf` at the location `/Dice.jl/results` inside the docker and at the location `${PWD}/results/` during and after running the docker image.

The results for figures 4a, 4b and 4c might vary due to WebPPL and Stan being stochastic tools. For figures 4a and 4b, we do not expect the baselines to identify both the modes at 5 and -5. For figure 4c, SMC should be able to identify both the modes. For figure 4d, the code should generate a smoother plot for AQUA but only identify the mode at 5.

2.2.5 Reproducing Figure 6

To generate the data and run different baselines, run the following command:

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure6/run.sh
3 $ python3 scripts/figure6/generate_plot.py
```

The above commands would generate the figure `conjugate_gaussians.png` at the location `/Dice.jl/results` inside the docker and at the location `${PWD}/results/` during and after running the docker image.

2.2.6 Reproducing Figure 12

To generate the data and run different baselines, run the following command. This would generate the plots `exp_results.png` and `var_results.png`.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure12/run.sh
```

2.2.7 Reproducing Figure 13

We have scripts specific to each benchmark which can be run using the following commands.

```
1 $ cd Dice.jl
2 $ scripts/figure13/altermu2.sh
3 $ scripts/figure13/addFun_max.sh
4 $ scripts/figure13/spacex.sh
5 $ scripts/figure13/weekend.sh
6 $ python3 scripts/figure13/generate_plot.py
```
